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PRODUCT BRANDING STRATEGY

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ABSTRACT

Brand is an intangible asset is often the most valuable asset on a corporation's balance sheet. Brand owners manage their brands carefully to create shareholder value, and brand valuation is an important management technique that ascribes a money value to a brand, and allows marketing investment to be managed (e.g.: prioritized across a portfolio of brands) to maximize shareholder value. Although only acquired brands appear on a company's balance sheet, the notion of putting a value on a brand forces marketing leaders to be focused on long term stewardship of the brand and managing for value. The most effective and useful way of communicating a brand to its customers is visualization. The primary concepts of visualization cannot be merely be understood with the help of books, but will have to be experienced in practical by visiting the brand or walking through a brand yatra.

Key Words- Brand, Strategy, Awareness

DEFINITION OF BRANDING:

A Brand is not a product or a promise or a feeling. It is the sum of all the experiences you have with a company.- Amir Kassaei

The process involved in creating a unique name and image for a product in the consumers' mind, mainly through advertising campaigns with a consistent theme. Branding aims to establish a significant and differentiated presence in the market that attracts and retains loyal customers.

WHAT IS BRANDING?:

To understand **branding**, it is important to know what brands are. A brand is the idea or image of a specific product or service that consumers connect with, by identifying the name, logo, slogan, or design of the company who owns the idea or image. Branding is when that idea or image is marketed so that it is recognizable by more and more people, and identified with a certain service or product when there are many other companies offering the same service or product. Advertising professionals work on branding not only to build brand recognition, but also to build good reputations and a set of standards to which the company should strive to maintain or surpass. Branding is an important part of Internet commerce, as branding allows companies to build their reputations as well as expand beyond the original product and service, and add to the revenue generated by the original brand.

When working on branding, or building a brand, companies that are using web pages and search engine optimization have a few details to work out before being able to build a successful brand. Coordinating domain names and brand names are an important part of finding and keeping visitors and clients, as well as branding a new company. Coordination of a domain name and brand names lends identification to the idea or image of a specific product or service, which in turn lets visitors easily discover the new brand.

Branding is also a way to build an important company asset, which is a good reputation. Whether a company has no reputation, or a less than stellar reputation, branding can help change that. Branding can build an expectation about the company services or products, and can encourage the company to maintain that expectation, or exceed them, bringing better products and services to the market place.

Brand is the "name, term, design, symbol, or any other feature that identifies one seller's product distinct from those of other sellers."^[1] Initially, branding was adopted to differentiate one person's cattle from another's by means of a distinctive symbol burned into the animal's skin with a hot iron stamp and was subsequently used in business, marketing, and advertising. A modern example of a brand is *Coca Cola* which belongs to the Coca-Cola Company.

In accounting, a brand defined as an The word "brand" is often used as a metonym referring to the company that is strongly identified with a brand.

Marque or make are often used to denote a brand of motor vehicle, which may be distinguished from a car model. A *concept brand* is a brand that is associated with an abstract concept, like breast cancer awareness or environmentalism, rather than a specific product, service, or business. A *commodity brand* is a brand associated with a commodity. Got milk? is an example of a commodity brand.

PRODUCT MEANS:

In marketing, a **product** is anything that can be offered to a market that might satisfy a want or need.^[1] In retailing, products are called merchandise. In manufacturing, products are bought as raw materials and sold as finished goods. Commodities are usually raw materials such as metals and agricultural products, but a commodity can also be anything widely available in the open market. In project management, products are the formal definition of the project deliverables that make up or contribute to delivering the objectives of the project. In insurance, the policies are considered products offered for sale by the insurance company that created the contract.

In economics and commerce, products belong to a broader category of goods. The economic meaning of product was first used by political economist Adam Smith.

DETERMINING BRAND'S OBJECTIVES:

Critical to effective brand management is the clear definition of the brand's audience and the objectives that the brand needs to achieve.

What are the objectives that you hope to achieve with your brand?

Your brand should be comprised of the company personality, image, core competencies and characteristics. The impressions that you make as well as the words people will use to describe your company to others, are the basic framework of your brand.

With a strong brand you build credibility, have more influence on your market, and motivate customers and clients to purchase from you. If done correctly your company will be looked at as a leader not a follower.

To determine your brand objectives ask yourself the following question:

- What is it that you want your brand to do for your company?
- What do you want others to know and say about your products or services?

SAMPLE OBJECTIVES MAY INCLUDE:

- Being recognized by receiving a specific award
- Picking up a certain number of choice projects
- Gaining a specific number of new clients in the next year
- Positioning your company as an industry leader in the next five months

You will find that by defining your objectives with specific timelines, it is easier to develop a plan of action to achieve those objectives. By defining your objectives you are able to map out a plan on how to achieve those objectives. Say for example your objective is to position your company as an industry leader. How can you go about doing this? You could:

- Have members of your team speak at Trade Shows
- Schedule lectures at professional group gatherings within your industry
- Write and publish articles in newspapers, magazines, or online media

Once you've determined your objectives the next step is to build and develop your brand strategy by listing out how, when, and what you are going to do to accomplish and meet your brand objectives.

Use the questions above to determine your brand objectives. List each objective and map out how you plan to accomplish and succeed in meeting those objectives. Don't stop there! Once you've finished take time to list out what you can do in this month or this quarter to meet that objective. Be specific and schedule those action items in your business calendar.

BRAND AWARENESS:

Brand awareness refers to customers' ability to recall and recognize the brand under different conditions and link to the brand name, logo, jingles and so on to certain associations in memory. It consists of both brand recognition and brand recall. It helps the customers to understand to which product or service category the particular brand belongs and what products and services are sold under the brand name. It also ensures that customers know which of their needs are satisfied by the brand through its products (Keller). Brand awareness is of critical importance since customers will not consider your brand if they are not aware of it.

There are various levels of brand awareness that require different levels and combinations of brand recognition and recall. Top-of-Mind is the goal of most companies. Top-of-mind awareness occurs when your brand is what pops into a consumer's mind when asked to name brands in a product category. For example, when someone is asked to name a type of facial tissue, the common answer is "Kleenex," which is a top-of-mind brand. **Aided Awareness** occurs when a consumer is shown or reads a list of brands, and expresses familiarity with your brand only after they hear or see it as a type of memory aide. **Strategic Awareness** occurs when your brand is not only top-of-mind to consumers, but also has distinctive qualities that stick out to consumers as making it better than the other brands in your market. The distinctions that set your product apart from the competition is also known as the Unique Selling

Point or USP. Marketing mix modeling can help marketing leaders optimize how they spend marketing monies to maximize the impact on Brand Awareness or sales effects. Managing brands for value creation will often involve applying marketing mix modeling techniques in conjunction with brand valuation.

WHAT IS BRANDING AND HOW IMPORTANT IS IT TO YOUR MARKETING STRATEGY?:

The American Marketing Association (AMA) defines a brand as a "name, term, sign, symbol or design, or a combination of them intended to identify the goods and services of one seller or group of sellers and to differentiate them from those of other sellers.

Therefore it makes sense to understand that branding is not about getting your target market to choose you over the competition, but it is about getting your prospects to see you as the only one that provides a solution to their problem.

The objectives that a good brand will achieve include:

- Delivers the message clearly
- Confirms your credibility
- Connects your target prospects emotionally
- Motivates the buyer
- Concretizes User Loyalty

To succeed in branding you must understand the needs and wants of your customers and prospects. You do this by integrating your brand strategies through your company at every point of public contact.

Your brand resides within the hearts and minds of customers, clients, and prospects. It is the sum total of their experiences and perceptions, some of which you can influence, and some that you cannot.

A strong brand is invaluable as the battle for customers intensifies day by day. It's important to spend time investing in researching, defining, and building your brand. After all your brand is the source of a promise to your consumer. It's a foundational piece in your marketing communication and one you do not want to be without.

What does branding mean to your company's marketing strategy? Post Questions, Comments, and Answers to this Question in the Marketing Forum.

WHAT ROLE DOES YOUR LOGO PLAY IN YOUR BRANDING STRATEGY?

When I speak about branding it's not uncommon for people to mistake their logo as their "branding". Your logo is only one piece of your branding strategy. Your logo is a symbol that can provide consumers with instant and powerful brand recognition of your business and the services or products that you offer.

Before beginning the process of logo creation be sure that you have developed your brand strategy. Why? Your logo is like a small ad for your company, without the strategy behind it a logo can put across the wrong message and in return weaken your strategy. You want to keep your brand message consistent to help increase consumer recognition.

HOW DO YOU KNOW WHEN YOU ARE READY TO MOVE TO THE PROCESS OF HAVING YOUR LOGO CREATED?

- The mission of your logo is to portray the values and goals of your company. Make sure that these are clearly established before venturing out to find a logo designer.
- Be clear about the message you want your brand to convey so that your logo can clearly reflect that message. You must have a strong association between your brand and your logo. Remember it is only one piece of your branding strategy.

- Your logo should reflect professionalism and growth no matter how small your company is.
- If you are designing your logo in-house to save money be sure to market-test your efforts.
- Make sure that the logo you select is not dated but can be used effectively year after year. Keep in mind it is how consumers will recognize your company.

The conclusion of the role your logo plays in your branding strategy can be summed up in the following statement.

Confident branding and a strong branding strategy uses design to communicate a message that attracts the target audience that you want to attract - a message that creates confidence in your brand while differentiating between you and your competitors. Does your logo fulfill this mission? If your answer is no it may be time to consider strengthening your brand strategy and looking at a new logo to re-position your company.

WHAT IS THE IMPORTANCE OF BRANDING IN MARKETING?

Once you realize that every successful business is grounded on its unique and appealing brand, there's no denying the importance of branding in marketing. The goal is to make it easy for consumers to relate your brand to a specific product or service. In this way, your company name, logo, and brand are not just symbols—they are the face of your company that customers picture when they require the product or service you offer.

Here are 4 reasons why you should work with a promotional marketing company to create a face for your business, no matter its size or scope. The importance of branding in marketing is clear if you want to connect with your customers without going broke in the process. If you can customize your brand according to the needs of your customer base, you will be well on your way to the success you crave for your business.

Create Business Credibility

If you can continually associate your brand with quality products and services, soon they will be one and the same in the minds of your customers. This credibility is not built overnight. You must prove that your business can continually innovate to provide top-notch customer service as well as products and services that are dependable.

Connect the Customer to the Product

You probably feel a connection with—and even a loyalty to—your favorite brands. They have helped you be successful in various aspects of your life. Products are the backbone of humankind's success, and every successful product is backed by a recognizable brand and a trustworthy company, which are the traits you need to create for your own business.

Motivate the Buyer

When the connection between the customer and the product is strong, the brand becomes a motivator for the customer to continue buying products, even if they have never used that exact product before. Your customer places trust in your brand and its quality so they know buying another product from the same brand is likely to deliver similar satisfaction.

CONCLUSION:

Well, thinking about branding resembles what a company is all about in the mind of its clients. Good branding differentiates the products and service in a positive way that actually sticks in the minds of potential customers.

A Brand hold the key to the success of a business in the long run. Gone are those day when the success of an organization was limited only to the quality of its product and services. Though quality is still an important indicator of success. customers nowadays prefer those brand which provide them with an overall great experience. Therefore, one of the major factors to ensure a brand to be a success is brand communication.

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